

Comparison of Nutrition and Concentration Analysis of Kanzaw Oil and Olive Oil by Using Microspectrophotometer UV-2550

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Abstract

Microspectrophotometer UV-2550 series are single beam spectrometers that analyze specimen materials in the ultraviolet and visible spectral range. UV-2550 series analyze the concentration morality (M), absorbent energy of the liquid, solid and so on. In this paper, the concentration and nutrition values of Kanzaw oil are compared with Olive oil by using Microspectrophotometer. From this result, it was found that concentrations and nutrition values of Kanzaw oil and Olive oil are nearly the same.

Introduction

Kanzaw (*Baccaurea ramiflora*) also known as Mahua in Myanmar grows naturally in the town like Myeik, Kawthaung and Palaw in Taninthayi region. They mostly grow in muddy areas, muddy areas where streams interception and Mangrove forest. We can get fruit from Kanzaw tree once for every three years. Seeds are dried by the sun and can make oil. Long ago, people used Kanzaw oil in cooking and thus they lived longer and healthier in their lives. Kanzaw Oil can cure diseases such as injury, cough and burn injury.

Olives (*Olea Europaea..Linn*) are a powerful and delicious fruit that can provide the human body with a wealth of health benefits including their ability to prevent bone loss, prevent various cancers, reduce inflammation and arthritis, improve digestion, soothe allergic reactions, improve blood circulation, protect against heart disease, boost cognitive function, defend against infections, and lower blood pressure. Olives are perhaps best known in the Eastern Mediterranean region, and although they are now available throughout the world, this is the area where they first came to prominence, as well as in the northern regions of Iraq and Iran.

They have been used for their culinary value and medicinal benefits for thousands of years, stretching all the way back to ancient times of Greece and Rome. The word "Olive" is actually derived from those languages, and it appears in literature and history of countless Mediterranean empires and cultures.

Olive oil gets a lot of attention because it is so functional in cooking, and is hailed as having a more concentrated form of nutrients than the Olive fruit itself, but it is important not to overlook the massive health benefits that all Olives possess. In this paper, I observed and compare about the concentration and absorbance of Kanzaw oil and Olive oil by using Microspectrophotometer UV-2550 series.

Fruits of Kanzaw are also utilized for human consumption as food. Unripe fruits are used for vegetable preparation in following way: Flesh of Kanzaw fruit covering hard seeds are first peeled off to remove outer thin portion and then remaining portion are cut into pieces and fried in small amount of mustard oil along with onion and garlic paste. It take appropriate amount of mixed spices powder and cook till complete softening of fruit pieces and also to prepare a concentrated curry of mixed spices. This vegetable is sometimes used as substitute of jackfruit.

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Olive oil has a long history of being used as a home remedy for skincare. Egyptians used it alongside beeswax as a cleanser, moisturizer, and antibacterial agent. In ancient Greece, the substance was used during massage, to prevent sports injuries, relieve muscle fatigue, and eliminate lactic acid buildup. In 2000, Japan was the top importer of Olive oil in Asia (13,000 tons annually) because consumers there believe both the ingestion and topical application of Olive oil to be good for skin and health.

Review of literature on chemical composition of Kanzaw flower reveals its high nutritional values. Apart from being a rich source of sugar and protein, the flowers also contain essential minerals like Ca, P, Fe and K. Calcium is the major component of bone and assists in teeth development. Phosphorus is next in importance to calcium as utilization of calcium is closely related to it. Most of the calcium in the body is deposited as calcium phosphate. Iron is an essential element for the formation of hemoglobin of red cells of blood. Vitamins like riboflavin and niacin content of the flower is more than that of apple, banana, mango and raisin (Table 1). Riboflavin as a part of a coenzyme is essential for several oxidation processes inside the cell and is concerned with energy and protein metabolism. Among several B-complex vitamins, riboflavin deficiency is most widespread, particularly among women and children, as it is the most limiting of all B-vitamins in cereal-based diet of the poor. Niacin is also an important vitamin intimately connected with several metabolic reactions.

Various compounds in Olives function not only as antioxidant compounds, but also anti-inflammatory ones. These reduce inflammation throughout the body after eating them, which includes a reduction in pain and irritation in the joints, muscles, injuries, tendons, and extremities which may suffer from various types of inflammation from a number of medical conditions. Olives are a healthy source of fiber, supplying almost 20% of the daily requirements for fiber in a single cup. Nutritional concentrations of Kanzaw oil and Olive oil are measured at FIDSL(UMFCCI) Yangon. From this results, it was found that Vitamin C is contain in only Kanzaw oil. Comparative of nutritional constituent of Kanzaw oil and Olive oil with other fruits was shown in table1.

Table 1. Comparative nutritional constituent of Kanzaw oil and Olive oil with other fruits

Per 100g	Apple (%)	Kanzaw (%)	Banana (%)	Olive (%)
Moisture	84.60	73.60	70.10	81.00
Protein	0.20	1.40	1.20	1.03
Fat	0.50	1.60	0.30	15.32
Minerals	0.30	0.70	0.80	104.00
Carbohydrates	13.40	22.70	27.20	3.84
Energy	59.00	111.00	116.00	146.00
Calcium	10.00	45.00	17.00	5.00
Phosphorus	14.00	22.00	36.00	1.00
Iron	0.66	0.23	0.36	4.00
Riboflavin	0.00	0.00	0.08	1.00
Vitamin C	1.00	40.00	7.00	0.00

Fig 1. Nutritional Comparative Chart of Kanzaw oil with Olive oil

Fig 2. Kanzaw's flowers, fruits and seeds

Microspectrophotometer UV-2550

UV-2550 is a traditional analytical device used in conventional laboratories. This spectrophotometer delivers enhanced user-friendliness, Precision and accuracy resulting in time and cost savings, as well as unprecedented confidence in test results. Microspectrophotometer UV-2550 works in the Ultra-violet and visible range of 190-1100 nm and has a fixed bandwidth of 2 nm. Microspectrophotometer UV-2550 offers high performance and reliability, which can be used in various applications. Microspectrophotometer UV-2550 can be used extensively for qualitative and quantitative analysis in such fields as clinical analysis, spectrochemistry laboratories, chemistry and biochemistry laboratories, as well as in quality control departments, i.e. environmental control, water management, food processing, and agriculture. Microspectrophotometer UV-2550 is equipped with the USB interface and port. Spectro UV-2550 can be linked to a computer, which is compatible with Windows Platforms, and a printer to display the photometric and spectral data on the PC monitor. Microspectrophotometer UV-2550 utilizes a new optical system design and is microcomputer controlled. This instrument has soft keys for ease of use. Microspectrophotometer UV-2550 has excellent baseline stability and high resolution. Microspectrophotometer UV-2550

consists of a light source (Tungsten Halogen and Deuterium lamp) which switches modes automatically, monochromator, Silicon photodiode, logarithmic amplifier, digital volt meter, D.C stabilizer, and microprocessor. This new generation instrument is equipped with a Microprocessor to automatically adjust 100 % T and Zero ABS, Factor, and Concentration. Microspectrophotometer UV-2550 operates with a single beam system and 1200 line grating mirror. Microspectrophotometer UV-2550 has a four digit display for automatic calculation and direct readout of Transmittance, Absorption, and Concentration. One of the most important features of the new Microspectrophotometer UV-2550 is that the light will change automatically from visible to UV as needed.

Fig 3. UV 2550 Micro-spectrophotometer

Fig 4. Cells container

There are two types of cells of the Microspectrophotometer. They are quartz cell and glass cell. Glass cell is only for visible region and quartz cell is ultra violet region. But quartz cell can be used visible region. Cell of the spectrometer was shown in figure 4.

Theory Background of Spectrometer

Spectrophotometry is the quantitative measurement of the reflection or transmission properties of a material as a function of wavelength. It is more specific than the general term electromagnetic spectroscopy in that spectrophotometry deals with visible light, near-ultraviolet, and near-infrared, but does not cover time-resolved spectroscopic techniques. Spectrophotometry uses photometers that can measure a light beam's intensity as a function of its color (wavelength) known as spectrophotometers. Important features of spectrophotometers are spectral bandwidth, (the range of colors it can transmit through the test sample), and the percentage of sample-transmission, and the logarithmic range of sample-absorption.

The fundamental law, which absorption methods are based on the Beer-Lambert relationship. This law states that the amount of light absorbed by a solution is an exponential function of concentration and path length of the solution.

$$-\frac{dp}{dN} = Kp$$

Where p is the radiant intensity, N is the number of absorbing species in the light path and K is the proportionality constant.

$$\frac{dp}{p} = -KdN$$

$$\ln \frac{p}{p_0} = -KN$$

Since N is the dependent on both the concentration 'c' and the path length 'b', then:
 $KN = k'bc$

K is often referred to as the absorptivity 'a' also includes a conversion from base 'e' to base 10 logs.

$$\text{Log} \frac{p}{p_0} = -abc$$

$\frac{p}{p_0}$ is a measure of the light passes through the solution is transmitted. $\frac{p}{p_0}$ is also called the transmittance (T).

For absorbance A is $-\log(T) = A$ So $A = abc$ (or) $A = \epsilon bc$

Where, A = absorbance (abs)

ϵ = absorptivity constant = 1.18×10^4 (abs $\text{cm}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}$)

b = cell path length (cm) = 1 cm

c = concentration morality (M)

There are two types of cells of the Microspectrophotometer. They are quartz cell and glass cell. Glass cell is only for visible region and quartz cell is ultra violet region. But quartz cell can be used visible region. Cell of the spectrometer was shown in figure 3.2.

While it is absorbance that is used to produce a relationship with concentration, it is transmittance that is directly measured. While most instruments will produce both types of numbers, it is better to read transmittance, if a meter is involved and then converted. Each instrument varies to extent so it is best to determine the absorptive using standard. We always attempt to work at the wavelength of maximum absorbance (λ_{max}). This is the point of maximum response so batter sensitivity and lower detection limits. The relation between the absorbance and transmittance were shown in figure 7.

Fig 5. The basic principle of Microspectrophotometer

Fig 6. The Cell of Microspectrophotometer

Fig 7. Relation between Transmittance and Absorbance

Result and Conclusion

Table 2. Concentration, Absorbance and Transmittance results of Kanzaw oil from UV-2550

Wavelength (nm)	Transmittance (%)	Absorbance (abs)	Concentration (M)
200	0.994	0.003	22.149
300	0.987	0.006	48.150
400	0.999	4.3×10^{-4}	3.682
500	1.000	0.000	0.000
600	1.000	0.000	0.000
700	0.999	4.3×10^{-4}	3.682
800	0.999	4.3×10^{-4}	3.682
900	0.999	4.3×10^{-4}	3.682
1000	0.999	4.3×10^{-4}	3.682
Average value			9.239

Fig 5. Wavelength Vs Transmittance and Absorbance graph of Kanzaw oil

Fig 6. Wavelength Vs Transmittance, Absorbance and Concentration graph of Kanzaw oil

Table 3. Concentration, Absorbance and Transmittance, results of Olive oil from UV-2550

Wavelength(nm)	Transmittance(%)	Absorbance (abs)	Concentration (M)
200	1.000	0.000	0.000
300	1.000	0.000	0.000
400	0.996	1.740×10^{-3}	14.751
500	0.999	4.3×10^{-4}	3.682
600	0.996	1.740×10^{-3}	14.751
700	0.998	8.694×10^{-4}	7.368
800	0.996	1.740×10^{-3}	14.751
900	0.999	4.3×10^{-4}	3.682
1000	0.999	4.3×10^{-4}	3.682
Average value			7.833

Fig 7. Wavelength Vs Transmittance and Absorbance graph of Olive oil

Fig 8. Wavelength Vs Concentration and Transmittance, Absorbance and Concentration graph of Olive oil

Conclusion

From these results, it was found that the concentration value of Kanzaw oil is 9.239M and Olive oil is 7.833M, that is significant of concentration of Kanzaw oil. And nutritional constituents are nearly the same too. There are so many examples of Olive oil using as like as Kanzaw oil. The health and medicinal benefits of Olives oil mainly come from its nutrients, vitamins, minerals, and organic compounds, including iron, fiber, copper, vitamin-E, phenol compounds, oleic acid, and a variety of antioxidants.

Kanzaw oil is very useful for our life and very good for our healthy. This plants are the important economical source of a number that will established drugs looking upon wide prospects and potential of Kanzaw for various purposes, it is worthwhile to cultivate this plant on large scale especially on unproductive. From this research have valuable knowledge of Kanzaw because of their effectiveness, easy availability, low cost and comparatively being devoid of toxic effect. Kanzaw oil has found several other activities have to be finding out.

Finally, we knew that the chemical and physical properties of Kanzaw oil and Olive oil are nearly the same.

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References

- Chaudhary Anu and Bhadari Anil. (2011). *“Hepatoprotective Activity of a Methanolic Extract of MadhucaIndica on Carbon Tetrachloride Induced Hepato toxicity in Rat”* pages 30-35.
- Das BK and Choudhary BK. (2010). *“Quantitative Estimation of Changes in Biochemical Constituents of Mahhua Flower during Post Harvest Storage”* (Journal of Food Processing and Preservation, pages 831-844).
- Khan Salehin and Zahan Dilara. (2011). *“Anti-hyperglycemic Activity Studies with Methanol Extract of MadhucaIndica”* (J. F. Gmel. Leaves and Paederia L. Stems in Mice. Advance in Natural and Applied science , pages 53-58).
- Kumar Pavan K and Vidyasagar G. (2011). *“Screening of ModhucaIndico for Antidiabetic Activity in Streptozotocin and Streptozotocin-Nicotinamide Induced Diabetic Rat”* (International Journal of Pharma Tech Research, pages 107-104).